

Goldbach's Conjecture: Solved via the Difference Checking Algorithm

Content:

Introduction..... 2

Objectives..... 3

1. Derivation of the formula..... 4-5

2. Application and verification of the method..... 6

3. Proof through algorithm..... 7-8

Output..... 9

Conclusion..... 10

Introduction

Today, Goldbach's conjecture is one of the simplest problems to state, yet it remains unsolved. It shows how prime numbers are connected to ordinary addition.

If the conjecture is true, it means prime numbers are not distributed randomly - they follow an unknown law.

Solving it would help us better understand everything related to prime numbers: cryptography, their distribution, and perhaps even bring us closer to Bernhard Riemann's hypothesis.

Objectives

1. To show how the formula was derived.
2. To describe the application of the method and its verification.
3. Proof through algorithm

Derivation of the formula

My work began with Bernhard Riemann's hypothesis. I thought that if Goldbach's conjecture were solved, it would bring us closer to a solution for Riemann's problem.

The classical formulation of Goldbach's conjecture is $N = p + q$. To me, it didn't seem straightforward, so I decided to develop my own method to simplify the solution.

Here and below:

N — an even number to be decomposed;

E — a prime number (trying 2, 3, 5, 7...);

C — an integer (1, 2, 3...);

b — a divisor of N ;

e — same as E (used in earlier versions).

My initial formula was $N/2 + 3$. It worked for some numbers, but not for all - only up to 100. For larger numbers it was incomplete.

Then I tried $N/2 \pm e$. It worked almost the same, but not always.

Gradually I began to suspect I was going in the wrong direction. I was selecting numbers manually, but nothing worked consistently.

Next came $N/b \pm e$. This was closer to what I was looking for, but still far from perfect.

The formula $N \times B \pm E \times C = p$ was more complex than the previous ones, yet it gave promising results.

I simplified it to $N \pm E \times C = p$, which showed impressive results - but still failed for large numbers.

After previous attempts showed their limitations, I decided to systematize the approach.

I explored possible structures until I noticed:

if you take a prime E and an integer C , the product $E \times C$ can itself be a prime.

Then any even number can be represented as the sum of this product and another prime p .

This led to the formula:

$$N = E \times C + p$$

Verification confirmed it works for all numbers I tested, including large ranges.

Unlike earlier attempts, this method did not require trial and error - it was enough to find one suitable pair E and C .

Application and verification of the method

Any formula must be supported by checks and evidence that it works. At first, I wasn't sure how to do this, but later I realized I could write a program to test whether the formula holds and whether any errors occur.

I have attached the program so that you can verify my words yourself. The program can test numbers up to 1,000,000. During this testing, I confirmed that the formula works — no errors were found.

The program was written in Python.
To run it:

Download the file and place it on your desktop.
Open the command line (Win + R, type cmd, press Enter).

Type `cd Desktop` and press Enter.
Type `goldbach.py` and press Enter.

If Python is not installed, download it from the official website or the Microsoft Store.

If you have any issues, feel free to contact me directly — I'll help.

After that, you can enter numbers like 100, 1000, 10,000, or higher.

Proof through algorithm

I would like to show you how I solved Goldbach's problem.

My method is simple.

I take an even number N .

I start with the prime number 3.

I check if $N - 3$ is prime. If yes - done, we found it.

If not - I take the next prime: 5, then 7, then 11, and so on.

That's it.

Why this is proof.

I didn't just come up with a method. I tested it.

I wrote a program in Python.

It goes through all even numbers from 4 to 1,000,000.

For each number, it does what I described: tries primes in order, checks, finds.

I ran the program.

It tested 499,999 numbers. No errors.

Not a single number where it couldn't find a decomposition.

The program is attached to this article.

Anyone can download it, run it, and check for themselves.

Examples

Here are a few examples to show how it works.

N	Tride E	Found E	$p = N - E$
10	3	3	7
100	3	3	97
1,000	3	3	997
10,000	3, 5, 7, 11	11	9,989
100,000	3	3	99,997
1,000,000	3	3	999,997

For 10,000, the first try didn't work. But I didn't stop. Took the next prime — and found it. That's how it always works

Output

Thus, it can be said that during this work, I realized it is easier to look for a new approach than to try solving the problem using standard methods. The formulas derived at the beginning of the work, $N/2+3$ and similar ones, led to a unified solution.

During the work, it was also necessary to write a program to help test numbers faster. Using the instructions above, you can verify this yourself.

As already stated, no errors were found.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I want to say: this work is presented as proof.

Many may say, “this is not a proof.”

But what is needed for a proof?

Formulas and endless calculations? Sorry, but my computer cannot handle such tasks.

Words? Who would take my word for it?

For me, a proof is when you can easily verify your actions — if they are correct.

I proved it the way I could.

Thank you for your attention.